

Synthesis, spectral characterization and single crystal X-ray structure of silver(I) complexes of naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)amine

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Abstract : Two Schiff bases ($L\alpha$ and $L\beta$) are synthesized from pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde and α -naphthyl or β -naphthylamine. Silver(I) complexes of composition $[Ag(L\alpha \text{ or } L\beta)_2](ClO_4)$ are synthesized and spectroscopically characterized. Single crystal X-ray study of $[Ag(L\beta)_2](ClO_4)$ has confirmed the structure. The ligands and complexes show luminescence property.

Keywords : Silver(I) complexes, Schiff base, X-ray crystal structure, naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)amine.

2,2'-Bipyridine (bpy), 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) and their derivatives are widely used in the synthesis of coordination complexes¹⁻⁹ because of their spectroscopy, photophysics and photochemistry, redox properties, supramolecular chemistry etc. The functional group is $-N=C-C=N-$ and the key feature of these heterocycles is their π -electron deficiency. Recent years have witnessed a great deal of interest in the synthesis of new ligands in the framework of diimine function ($-N=C-C=N-$). The number of heteroatoms, ring size and substituents in the heterocyclic ring significantly modify and regulate the physical and chemical properties of the compounds¹⁰. The condensation of pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde with aromatic amines have synthesized Schiff bases containing $-N=C-C=N-$ group, in which in-built C=N group in pyridine ring is conjugated with exocyclic C=N group¹¹. It is surprising that naphthyl amines have been used in limited cases to synthesise diimine function^{12,13}. Naphthyl group is a sterically crowded, electronically labile and more delocalised than aryl group. This has encouraged us to extend this idea towards diimine system. In this work we wish to report spectroscopy and structural characterization of silver(I) complex of pyridyl-2-(α/β -naphthylmethylene)amine (α/β -NaiPy).

Results and discussion

Two ligands pyridyl-2-(α -naphthylmethylene)amine, α -NaiPy ($L\alpha$) and pyridyl-2-(β -naphthylmethylene)amine, β -NaiPy ($L\beta$) are used for the present work. These were synthesized by reacting pyridine 2-carboxaldehyde and α -naphthyl amine for α -NaiPy and β -naphthyl amine for β -NaiPy in 1 : 1 mole ratio in dry ethanol solution under reflux. The compound is recrystallised from ethanol-chloroform mixture.

Molecular structure of $[Ag(L\beta)_2](ClO_4)$ (2) :

The crystal structure is shown in Fig. 1 and metric parameters are listed in Table 1. The molecular disposition is analogous to $Ag(1\text{-ethyl-2-(naphthyl-}\alpha\text{-azo)imidazole})_2(ClO_4)$ ¹⁴. The structure shows a distorted tetrahedral geometry around Ag^I with AgN_4 coordination sphere. The ligand $L\beta$ serves as diimine type ($-N=C-C=N-$) chelating agent. Two atomic groups Ag, N(1), N(2), C(5), C(6) (plane-1, mean deviation $< 0.03\text{\AA}$) and Ag, N(3), N(4), C(21), C(22) (plane-2, mean deviation $< 0.03\text{\AA}$) constitute chelate planes and make dihedral of 77.13° . The pendant β -naphthyl group does not coplanar with the respective chelate ring; β -naphthyl group attached to plane-1 makes dihedral $7.68 (16)^\circ$ while other β -naphthyl attached to plane-2 makes dihedral

15.86 (16) $^\circ$. Two naphthyl rings are closer to orthogonal arrangement (dihedral angle 84.53 (18) $^\circ$). Two chelate angles are closely spaced : $\angle N(1)-Ag-N(2)$, 73.00 (9) $^\circ$ and $\angle N(3)-Ag-N(4)$, 71.87 (10) $^\circ$. However, these bite angles are deviated from regular pentagonal angle. This may cause distortion to the geometry. Other angles around Ag are also deviated from tetrahedral value such as, $\angle N(1)-Ag-N(3)$, 145.54 (10) $^\circ$; $\angle N(4)-Ag-N(2)$, 121.04 (9) $^\circ$. The Ag–N distances are also unequal and data are consistent in the respective chelate rings. In one chelate ring the Ag–N(pyridine) and Ag–N(imine) distances are closer to each other (Ag–N(1),

Fig. 1. ORTEP diagram with 50% probability for $[Ag(L\beta)_2](ClO_4)$.

2.325(3); Ag–N(2), 2.318(3) Å. In the second chelate ring the distances are significantly separated : Ag–N(3), 2.241(3); Ag–N(4), 2.455(3) Å. The C–N distances differ insignificantly in the chelate rings (C(6)–N(2), 1.270(4) and C(22)–N(4), 1.263(4) Å). We do not have free ligand value to compare the distances in the chelated unit. Packing view (Fig. 2) of the structure shows both hydrogen bonding and π – π interactions. Hydrogen bonding is observed with ClO_4^- (C(24)–H(24)–O(1)– ClO_3 ; C(24)–H(24), 0.91 Å; H(24)–O(1), 2.390(4) Å; C(24)–O(1), 3.291(7) Å; $\angle C-H-O$, 172.2(7) $^\circ$) and naphthyl hydrogen. Significant π – π interactions are observed between chelate ring and naphthyl ring of neighbouring molecule, pyridine ring and naphthyl ring of nearest neighbour as well as two naphthyl rings of two adjacent molecules (Table 2). However, effective interaction at low angle value ($\alpha = 0.02^\circ$) is observed between two naphthyl rings at a distance of 3.691 Å. These non-covalent interactions provide requisite rigidity to the structures.

Spectroscopic studies :

Infrared spectra of ligands (L) and complexes $[Ag(L)_2](ClO_4)$ exhibit strong stretches at 1620–1590 and 1600–1580 cm^{-1} , which suggest the presence of $\nu(C=N)$ in the compounds. In complexes the band is shifted to lower wavelength region in support of coordination of imine-N to Ag^I . A very strong band appear at 1100 cm^{-1} with a weak signal at 625 cm^{-1} is due to $\nu(ClO_4)$.

The electronic spectra of the complexes in CH_3CN

Fig. 2. Packing view of the structure

show weak absorption at 400–420 nm ($\epsilon \sim 10^3 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$) along with intense absorption in the UV region at ca. 380 and 330 nm ($\epsilon \sim 10^4 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$). This intense transition may be assigned to intraligand charge transfer ($n-\pi^*$ and $\pi-\pi^*$) transitions. The longer wave length weak transition may be due to d^{10} (Ag) to π^* state of diimine function. The complexes show small bathochromic shift (8–12 nm) on comparing with free ligands, indicating a weak interaction between Ag^+ and the ligands.

Fig. 3. Emission spectra of $L\alpha$ (–), $L\beta$ (---), $[Ag(L\alpha)_2](ClO_4)$ (-.-) and $[Ag(L\beta)_2](ClO_4)$ (....) in CH_3CN at room temperature (298 K).

The 1H NMR spectra are recorded in $CHCl_3$ solution. Data are given in experimental section. The assignment has been made on the basis of spin-spin interaction, and on

comparing with free ligand values. Pyridyl-2-(naphthylmethylene)amines exhibit a singlet at most down field and has assigned to -HC=N- (7H) at 8.75–8.78 ppm. Other signals at 7.7–8.5 ppm refer to pyridine-H (3-H-6-H) and naphthyl signals appear in the upper field side, 7.2–7.6 ppm. In complexes the NMR signals are in general down-field shifted. Of them the pyridyl protons (3-H to 6-H) are shifted to down field by >0.5 ppm from that of free ligand data. Naphthyl protons (8-H to 15-H) are shifted in significantly.

Table 1. Selected bond length (Å) and bond angles (°)

	Bond length (Å)	Bond angle (°)
Ag-N(1)	2.325(3)	N(1)-Ag-N(2) 73.00(9)
Ag-N(3)	2.241(3)	N(3)-Ag-N(4) 71.87(10)
Ag-N(2)	2.318(3)	N(1)-Ag-N(3) 145.54(10)
Ag-N(4)	2.455(3)	N(1)-Ag-N(4) 108.10(9)
N(2)-C(16)	1.270(4)	N(2)-Ag-N(4) 121.04(9)
N(4)-C(22)	1.263(4)	N(2)-Ag-N(3) 137.96(10)
Cl-O(1)	1.352(4)	C(5)-N(1)-Ag 112.6(2)
Cl-O(2)	1.422(4)	C(21)-N(3)-Ag 117.2(2)
Cl-O(3)	1.410(3)	O(1)-Cl-O(4) 114.8(3)
Cl-O(4)	1.393(4)	O(3)-Cl-O(2) 107.5(3)
π - π Distances		
Cg(1)---Cg(J)	Angle (°)	Cg---Cg (Å)
Cg(1)---Cg(5)	7.68	3.604
Cg(1)---Cg(6)	6.24	3.702
Cg(3)---Cg(6)	4.92	3.866
Cg(5)---Cg(6)	1.57	3.724
Cg(7)---Cg(7)	0.02	3.691
Cg(1) : Ag, N(1), C(5), C(6), N(2)		
Cg(3) : N(1), C(1), C(2), C(3), C(4), C(5)		
Cg(5) : C(7), C(8), C(9), C(14), C(15), C(16)		
Cg(6) : C(9), C(10), C(11), C(12), C(13), C(14)		
Cg(7) : C(23), C(24), C(25), C(26), C(27), C(28), C(29), C(30), C(31), C(32)		

Photoluminescence properties :

The photoluminescence properties of the ligands and complexes were studied at room temperature (Fig. 3). The Schiff bases exhibit photoluminescence with emission at 414 and 405 nm for $L\alpha$ and $L\beta$, respectively at room temperature in CH_3CN solution upon excitation at 330 nm. No emissions originating from metal-centred and MLCT or LMCT excited states are expected for the Ag^I complexes, since Ag^I ion is difficult to oxidize due to its d^{10} configuration. Thus, the emission observed in the complexes at 425 and 410 nm for $[\text{Ag}(L\alpha)_2](\text{ClO}_4)$ and $[\text{Ag}(L\beta)_2](\text{ClO}_4)$ respectively at 298 K are tentatively assigned to the $(\pi-\pi^*)$ intraligand fluorescence. At low temperature (77 K) : these four compounds exhibit enhanced emission at longer wave length ($L\alpha$: 418, $L\beta$: 410; $[\text{Ag}(L\alpha)_2](\text{ClO}_4)$: 445 and $[\text{Ag}(L\beta)_2](\text{ClO}_4)$: 440 nm). It has been reported that the metal ions can enhance or quench the fluorescence emission of pyridine containing compounds¹⁵. In the absence of metal ions the fluorescence of ligand is probably quenched

by the occurrence of a photoinduced electron transfer (PET) process due to the presence of a lone pair of nitrogen atoms. Such a PET process is prevented by the complexation of L with metal ions; due to rigidity of the chelate ring. This enhances fluorescence intensity upon coordination to metal ion.

Table 2. Summarised crystallographic data for $[\text{Ag}(L\beta)_2](\text{ClO}_4)$ (2)

	$[\text{Ag}(L\beta)_2](\text{ClO}_4)$
Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{ClAg}$
Formula weight	671.87
Temperature (K)	293(2)
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	P-1
Crystal size (mm^3)	$0.25 \times 0.20 \times 0.10$
Unit cell dimensions	
<i>a</i> (Å)	8.3730(10)
<i>b</i> (Å)	13.0970(6)
<i>c</i> (Å)	13.5600(10)
α (°)	100.784(5)
β (°)	94.478(8)
γ (°)	100.645(6)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1425.8(2)
<i>Z</i>	2
λ (Å)	0.70930
μ ($\text{Mo-K}\alpha$) (mm^{-1})	0.846
<i>D</i> _{calc} (g cm^{-3})	1.565
Refine parameters	475
Total data collected	4503
Unique data	3854
R_1^a [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	0.0351
wR_2^b	0.0847
Goodness of fit ^c	1.035

^a $R_1 = \sum |F_o - F_c| / \sum F_o$.

^b $wR_2 = [\sum (F_o^2 - F_c^2) / \sum w F_o^4]^{1/2}$, $w = 1/[\sigma^2(F^2) + (0.0473P)^2 + (1.0506P)]$

^cGoodness-of-fit is defined as $[\sum (F_o - F_c)^2 / n_v]^{1/2}$ where n_o and n_v denote the number of data and variables, respectively.

Experimental

Materials :

α -Naphthyl amine and β -naphthyl amine were purchased from Thomas Baker & Co, India. Pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde is an Aldrich reagent. All other chemicals used were of A.R. quality and were used as received.

Physical measurements :

UV-Vis spectra were recorded using JASCO UV-VIS-NIR V-570 spectrophotometer and infrared spectra were obtained from JASCO FTIR-420 instrument. Microanalyses were collected from Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHN/S elemental analyser. Fluorescence spectra were recorded using LS-55 Luminescence Spectrometer, Perkin-Elmer at room temperature and 77 K. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded from Bruker 300 MHz FT-NMR. Solution conductivity was measured in Systronics 305 digital conductivity meter.

Preparation of pyridyl-2-(α / β -naphthylmethylene)amine :

To a dry ethanolic solution of naphthylamine (1 g, 0.699 mol) in 50 ml pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde (0.75 g, 0.699 mol) was added. Triethylamine (0.71 g, 0.699 mol) was added to the ethanolic solution. The reaction mixture was stirred for 4 days. A light yellow precepitation comes down and filtered. The precepitation was washed with EtOH and hexane respectively. In both cases of α / β -naphthylamine yield was 1.05 g (\approx 55%). Melting point of pyridyl-2-(α -naphthylmethylene)amine (L α) and pyridyl-2-(β -naphthylmethylene)amine (L β) are gum and 88 °C respectively.

Microanalytical data : L α : Anal. Cal. for C₁₆H₁₂N₂; C, 82.8; H, 5.2; N, 12.1. Found : C, 82.7; H, 5.15; N, 12.0%. UV-Vis spectral data (CH₃CN, λ_{\max} (nm) ($10^{-3} \epsilon$ (dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)) : L α : 338 (17.28), 300 (16.17), 258 (44.57). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) (δ , ppm (J, Hz)) : 7.88 (3-H, d, 7.5), 7.80 (4-H, m), 7.80 (5-H, m), 8.41 (6-H, d, 7.5), 8.75 (7-H, s), 7.58 (9-H, d, 8.0), 7.18 (15-H, d, 8.0), 7.40–7.50 (10-14-H, m). L β : Anal. Cal. for C₁₆H₁₂N₂; C, 82.8; H, 5.2; N, 12.1. Found : C, 82.6; H, 5.1; N, 12.0%. UV-Vis spectral data (CH₃CNB, λ_{\max} (nm) ($10^{-3} \epsilon$ (dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)) : 344 (9.18), 288 (12.61), 258 (59.79). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) (δ , ppm (J, Hz)) : 7.65 (3-H, d, 8.0), 7.60 (4-H, m), 7.60 (5-H, m), 8.57 (6-H, d, 8.0), 8.78 (7-H, s), 7.56 (8-H, d, 8.0), 7.11 (15-H, d, 8.0), 7.30–7.50 (10-14-H, m).

Synthesis of [Ag(pyridyl-2-(β -naphthylmethylene)amine)₂](ClO₄)₂, [Ag(L β)₂](ClO₄) (2) :

Pyridyl-2-(β -naphthylmethylene)amine (0.5 g, 2.16 mmol) in MeOH (10 cc) was added dropwise to a methanolic solution (10 cc) of AgNO₃ (0.17 g, 1 mmol) at room temperature and stirred for 2 h covered with carbon paper to prevent photodecomposition. The volume of brown-red solution was reduced to half of its original volume by slow evaporation in air. An aqueous solution of NaClO₄ (0.5 g in 2 ml water) was added to this solution and kept refrigerator maintaining temperature at 5 °C. The bright yellow crystalline product was then filtered, washed with water and cold methanol. The compound was then purified by recrystallisation by diffusing CH₂Cl₂ solution into hexane. The yield was 0.38 g, 57%.

[Ag(L α)₂](ClO₄) (1) was also prepared similarly in the yield of 58%. Anal. Cal. for C₃₂H₂₄N₄O₄ClAg (1) : C, 57.19; H, 3.57; N, 8.34. Found : C, 57.04; H, 3.63; N, 8.45. Cal. for C₃₂H₂₄N₄O₄ClAg (2) : C, 57.19; H, 3.57; N, 8.34. Found : C, 57.00; H, 3.53; N, 8.40. UV-Vis spectral data (CH₃CN, λ_{\max} (nm) ($10^{-3} \epsilon$ (dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)) : 1 : 420 (4.73), 380 (16.89), 340 (11.49), 332 (12.25); 2, 405 (2.58), 388 (10.00), 340 (13.64), 328 (14.81). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) (δ ,

ppm (J, Hz)) : 1 : 8.06 (3-H, d, 7.2), 7.79 (4-H, t, 7.5), 8.00 (5-H, t, 9.0), 8.55 (6-H, d, 8.0), 8.85 (7-H, s), 7.72 (9-H, d, 8.0), 7.64 (10-H, m), 7.30–7.45 (11-15-H, m), 2 : 8.01 (3-H, d, 7.5), 7.85 (4-H, t, 7.5), 7.90 (5-H, t, 9.0), 8.51 (6-H, d, 8.0), 8.81 (7-H, s), 8.85 (8-H, broad), 7.63 (10-H, d, 8.0), 7.30–7.50 (11-15-H, m) (d = doublet, t = triplet, m = multiplet, s = singlet).

Crystallographic data collection and refinement :

Crystal suitable for X-ray work was grown by slow diffusion of CH₂Cl₂ solution of [Ag(L β)₂](ClO₄) (2) in hexane. Crystal size was 0.25 × 0.20 × 0.10 mm. Data were collected on an Enraf-Nonius CAD-4 diffractometer with graphite monochromatized MoK α radiation (λ = 0.70930 Å) at 293(2) K. Crystal data and collection parameter are listed in Table 1. The data were corrected for absorption effects by empirical method using azimuthal scan data. Of the 4503 collected reflections 3854 with $I > 2\sigma(I)$ were used for structure solution. The structure was solved by conventional direct method and refined by full-matrix least-square method on all F_o^2 data. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. The hydrogen atoms were fixed geometrically and refined using riding model. In the final difference Fourier map the residual maxima and minima were 0.567 and -0.424 eÅ⁻³. All calculations were carried out using SHELXL-97¹⁶, ORTEP-32¹⁷, PLATON-99¹⁸ programs.

Conclusion :

The work describes synthesis of pyridyl Schiff bases of naphthylamines. The ligands act as diimine type N, N chelator. Ag^I complexes of the Schiff base are synthesized and have been characterized by spectroscopic techniques. The structural confirmation has been carried out by single crystal X-ray diffraction study. Photoluminescence property of the ligands and complexes are also examined.

Supplementary material :

Crystallographic data for the structural analysis has been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic data centre, CCDC No. 288381 [Ag(L β)₂](ClO₄). Copies of this information may be obtained free of charge from the Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1FZ, UK (e-mail : deposit@ccdc.ac.uk).

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